

Conservancy of metabolic pathways across microbial genera

Gaétane Magali Sallard¹ | Lab rotation review 18.03. – 10.05.2024, Prof. Dr. A. Murat Eren² |
Supervised by Dr. Iva Veseli³

¹ Max Planck Institute for Marine Microbiology

^{1,2,3} Helmholtz Institute for Functional Marine Biodiversity Oldenburg

Abstract

Microbial metabolism, a crucial process supporting all kinds of microbial life, can now be analyzed across a wide range of taxa thanks to large, publicly available resources like the Genome Taxonomy Database (GTDB). However, many tools available to study microbial metabolism tend to overlook the dynamics of microbes on such a large scale. In this study, we introduce a universal metric expressing the conservancy of metabolic pathways in microbial genera. We computed weighted arithmetic means of genome completeness and pathway annotation quality. We used identity scores to distinguish between absent and undetected pathways, which allowed us to gain a better understanding of metabolic pathway preservation than with conventional threshold-based methods. By considering enzyme presence and functional significance based on genomic context, we demonstrate that applying our metric to larger datasets can unveil novel microbial capabilities. We provide an example of the genus *Forsterrea* to showcase the effectiveness of our approach. Overall, our study highlights the importance of considering pathway conservancy while analyzing microbial metabolism and introduces a new metric that could enhance our understanding of microbial capabilities.

Introduction

Metabolism is the essential process that supports life's flourishing¹. It is also the most studied biological system to date, which has led to significant scientific breakthroughs¹. For example, it has helped revolutionize the strategies used for bioremediation in environmental cleanup² and facilitated the development of new pharmaceuticals that target metabolic pathways to treat diseases³. With the advancements in genome sequencing and artificial intelligence, we are now dealing with big data and a constant influx of new genomes.

It is now possible to analyze microbial metabolism within a wide taxonomic range using large, publicly-available resources such as the Genome Taxonomy Database (GTDB)⁴. Consequently, there has been increased interest in exploring the effects of selection pressures on metabolic pathways of sequenced microorganisms¹. Studying

selection pressures on metabolic pathways can help researchers understand how organisms adapt to their environments, providing insights into functional and structural⁵ changes over time. Multiple resources are now accessible that offer detailed information about the metabolic profile of different microbes^{1,6–10}. These resources are based on the creation of metabolic networks, which are usually constructed using enzyme annotation and sequence similarity analysis of known enzymes mapped against their genomes.

Although there are many tools that focus on studying microbial metabolism at an individual or cellular level, we often overlook the dynamics of microbes on a larger scale. A study from Pererín-Alvarez J et al. has even attempted to analyze metabolic conservation by assessing the number of isoenzymes in a pathway across various taxa¹. However, this kind of method

does not account for the quantitative differences in enzyme abundance or activity levels among different organisms. In this study, we have developed a universal metric to evaluate the conservancy of metabolic pathways in microbial genera. To determine pathway conservancy, we use annotation. We differentiate between absent and undetected pathways and provide a quantitative measure of pathway conservancy that considers enzyme presence and their functional significance based on genomic context. weighted arithmetic means, which takes into account the degree of completeness of each genome and the quality of its pathway.

Creating a universal metric

In this study, we focused on the conservancy of microbial metabolic pathways at the genus level. This helped us account for similarities due to phylogenetic autocorrelation and differences in individual metabolic capabilities found on a species level. We, therefore, expect core pathways to be preserved within the genus, despite variations in each organism's metabolic abilities.

We focused on two core metabolic pathways for the first data analysis: glycolysis and photosynthesis. We predicted both pathways to be highly conserved. Glycolysis is omnipresent in all microorganisms¹¹, and photosynthesis is a present pathway in all organisms that convert light energy into chemical energy¹². Analyzing these specific pathways provided a strategic starting point for exploring less evident metabolisms. We extracted the *Pseudomonas* and *Prochlorococcus* genera from the GTDB v214 module database⁴, as we know that these genera both have genes for glycolysis, and the *Prochlorococcus* have photosynthetic capabilities.

We used the *anvi'o* program¹³, *anvi-gen*-contigs-database to convert each fasta file into a contigs databases with default parameters. We also performed a gene-calling step with *Prodigal*¹⁴ by annotating each genome with KEGG KOfams¹⁵ through *anvi-run-kegg-kofams*, and with microbial single-copy core genes (SCGs) using *anvi-run-hmms*. The sources of SCGs were derived from Campbell et al¹⁶. We used the *anvi-estimate-metabolism* program¹⁷, to estimate the completeness of metabolic pathways, which provided us with pathwise completeness scores for each metabolic pathway in the KEGG MODULE database¹⁸.

In the first stage of our analysis, we used Principal Components Analysis (PCA) to identify the main parameters that summarize the genetic conservancy of glycolysis and photosynthesis in both genera. We used the pathwise score as the central variable and based the structure of all other variables around it. This approach allowed us to recognize the connection between genome completeness and pathwise score and establish suitable thresholds to indicate genomic conservancy.

Conservancy of metabolic pathways across microbial genera

Figure 1 expected difference between pathwise and genome completeness scores

Our hypothesis assumes a linear relationship between the completeness and pathwise scores of genomes. If a genome is whole, we expect the pathway to be present and the corresponding pathwise score to take the same value. This expectation is represented by a red line, indicating that the difference between genome completeness and pathwise score is zero. Black dots illustrate the actual distribution from both core pathways glycolysis and photosynthesis. We observed that scores above a genome completeness level of 80% were less deviant from the expected distribution than those at a lower completeness level. Therefore, we set a genome completeness threshold of 80% for our analysis, for which we believe the pathway to be present. 1

To define an appropriate threshold for pathway conservancy, we compared genome completeness and pathwise scores for glycolysis in each microbial genome. Our hypothesis suggests a direct correlation between genome and pathwise completeness scores, and we accordingly inferred that a pathway must be conserved entirely in a fully conserved genome. In cases where the genome completeness scores are lower, it is possible that the enzymes responsible for a particular pathway may be missing.

Figure 1 Glycolysis - comparison of genome completeness and pathwise scores

We compared genome completeness (pink) and pathwise scores (violet) for glycolysis in each microbial genome. The degree of their difference is illustrated as a red line. Based on these differences, we have determined that a pathwise score of 0.75 is a suitable threshold for our analysis. We identify a smaller degree of difference between both values at this threshold.

Figure 1 depicts our hypothesis, with the expected difference between pathwise and genome completeness scores equalling 0 (indicated by the red line). Values above a genome completeness score of 80% deviated less from the expected distribution than those at lower completeness scores. Therefore, we restricted our analysis to a genome completeness threshold of 80%. Figure 2 illustrates the disparity between the genome completeness and pathwise scores, shown in pink and violet, respectively. Based on this graph, we have determined that a pathwise score of 0.75 is a suitable threshold for identifying smaller degrees of differences between the data points.

Our first algorithm was developed using the pre-established thresholds to filter for genome completeness and pathway scores. We considered a pathway to be present if its genome completeness score was equal to or greater than 80% and its pathwise score was equal to or greater than 75%. If these criteria were not met, we regarded the pathway as absent. It is important to note that this model operates on binary data and filters a considerable amount of data on the genomic taxonomic level prior to the algorithmic stage.

$$P = \begin{cases} \text{FALSE,} & \text{if } C < T_C \\ \text{TRUE,} & \text{if } C \geq T_C \text{ and } P \geq T_P \\ \text{FALSE,} & \text{if } C \geq T_C \text{ and } P < T_P \end{cases}$$

C genome completeness (%),
 P pathwise score,
 T_C genome completeness threshold (80%),
 T_P pathwise score threshold (0.75)

Figure 2 Presence (P) of a Pathway based on thresholds

The pathway's presence is represented by a boolean value: TRUE or FALSE.

The subsequent goal was to determine the level of pathway conservancy within a genus and define within-group pathway conservancy, for which we developed two methods – the first based on the binary TRUE/FALSE results obtained from the prior threshold definition and the second based on genome identity scores. To achieve this, we clustered identical genome IDs as a species using their weighted arithmetic mean μ to account for the effect of species with fewer genomes. Furthermore, we regarded single genomes as a species. In a second step, we used the weighted species means to find metabolic pathway conservancy up to the genus taxonomic level. To do this, we introduced the weighted mean μ' of a genus (i) using a factor w that would allow us to weigh each species differently for each genus. A more detailed report of our approach is emphasized in the information box below.

Hence, we introduce a novel metric (VI) that effectively summarizes the conservancy of metabolic pathways across diverse genera and is applicable to the complete tree of life. The application of our metric results in μ' (genus weighted mean) values ranging from 0 to 1. A high μ' value (0.6 -1) indicates a highly conserved pathway and lower μ' values (0-0.4) therefore indicate a poor pathway conservancy. The values are stored in a matrix format, which allows for further data analysis.

 In Detail

To determine the species mean μ , we iterate through all the genome IDs in the GTDB dataset and group identical IDs together. Each unique ID is treated as a separate species. For each species, we developed two methods to compute its mean. Our first method (I). uses predefined thresholds, mentioned in page 4 and computes the mean of a species by taking a weighted average μ of the binary presence/absence score of each of its genomes (where T is 1 and F is 0). Our second method does not involve prior filtering of data and the definition of thresholds. Instead, we compute the weighted mean of a species based on the identity and pathwise score of each genome (II). The identity score is determined based on four main factors. When a genome has a high completeness score and a high pathwise score, it is highly likely that the pathway will be present, resulting in a high identity score. Conversely, if a genome has a high completeness score but a low pathwise score, it is highly probable that the pathway will not be present. On the other hand, if a genome has a low completeness score but a high pathwise score, we can assume with confidence that the pathway will be present. However, in cases where a genome has a low completeness score and a low pathwise score, this information is insufficient for analysis and should be disregarded. We therefore selected the identity score I_i as the maximum value between the pathwise score and the completeness score. For instance, if a pathwise score of a certain genome has a value of 0.5, and it's completeness score of 1, then the I_i value will be defined as 1, since it is the more significant value between the two.

$$\text{I) } \mu_{sp.i} = \frac{1}{n_{genomes}} * \sum_{i=1}^{n_{genomes}} x_i, x \in [T(1), F(0)]$$

$$\text{II) } \mu_{sp.i} = (I_i^2 / \sum I_i^2) * P_i$$

In equation III, we summarize the conservancy of metabolic pathways across genera by taking the weighted means of our species means μ defined in equation I or II. To do this, we introduce a factor w that allows us to weigh each species differently for each genus. The parameters for w are clarified in IV, as it is dependent on the number of species present in the dataset. To mitigate the effect of the number of genomes per species on the genus level, we use a square root term to define the function g (V).

$$\text{III) } \mu'_{genus.i} = \sum_{i=1}^{n_{species.i}} w_i * \mu_{species.i}$$

$$\text{IV) } w_i = \frac{g(n_{species.i})}{\sum_{j=1}^N g(n_{species.i})}$$

$$\text{V) } g(n_i) = \sqrt{n_i}$$

The summary of these parameters result in a universal metric that can portray the conservancy of metabolic pathways across genera, as illustrated in equation VI.

VI)

$$\mu'_{genus.i} = \sum_{i=1}^{n_{species.i}} \frac{\sqrt{n_{genomes.i}}}{\sum \sqrt{n_{genomes.i}}} * \mu_{species.i}$$

Applications

We tested the effectiveness of our metric across microbial genera by conducting a trial experiment with a collection of 38972 genome sequences extracted from the GTDB v214 module database⁴. The genomes belonged to different species of five bacterial and five archaeal genera. We aimed to validate the ability of our metric to illustrate the conservancy of metabolic pathways in each genus. We used filtering and non-filtering methods explained in the information box on page 5 to achieve this. Once we applied our metric to this dataset, we obtained a matrix with ten genera and 323 unique pathway entries, each containing a conservancy value. Figures 4 and 5 below show the outcome of the experiment. For Figure 4, we filtered the data using thresholds described in x to the dataset beforehand. The metabolic pathway conservancy is colour-coded with lighter shades indicating higher conservancy levels, and darker shades indicating lower conservancy levels. The ordering of the genera in both figures is based on their relatedness, as illustrated by the phylogenetic tree on the left. To achieve this, we used the ribosomal sequence of a representative genome of each genus to construct an approximately-maximum-likelihood phylogenetic tree using FastTree, which we then rooted with FigTree.

Our visualization reveals a significant impact of the utilization of thresholds (as shown in Figure 4) on the pathway conservancy values. While some core pathways remain somewhat preserved,

several pathways are lost with this method. For instance, a vital pathway like pyrimidine ribonucleotide biosynthesis remains relatively conserved with this approach, which is crucial in cellular processes such as DNA and RNA synthesis¹⁹. Nonetheless, this method has severe limitations when analyzing metabolic pathway conservancy. It can result in losing important information, such as the overall conservancy of PRPP (5-phosphoribosyl-1-pyrophosphate) biosynthesis, which is highly conserved across genera in our model using identity scores (as shown in Figure 5). This pathway is an essential precursor for DNA and RNA biosynthesis in microorganisms²⁰.

The archaeal genus *Forsterrea* well exemplifies the limitations of using thresholds. Figure 5 shows that PRPP, pyruvate oxidation, and nucleotide degradation pathways are highly conserved in *Forsterrea* when we do not filter the data beforehand. However, when we set thresholds, all pathways appear to be non-conserved. This limitation is due to *Forsterrea's* low genome completeness scores. We assume low pathway conservancy by setting thresholds, even if *Forsterrea's* pathwise scores equal 1.0, indicating that the pathway is ultimately conserved. Furthermore, the genome sequences of *Forsterrea* are significantly small, with an average of 800,000 base pairs²¹. The fact that PRPP, pyruvate oxidation, and nucleotide degradation are highly conserved in Figure 5 suggests that it could be a crucial pathway for *Forsterrea*.

Based on the size of *Forsterrea's* genomes and the lack of conservancy of other pathways, these could be significant metabolic investments that could give *Forsterrea* a competitive edge. One possible explanation is the symbiotic relationship between *Forsterrea* and another organism. Our hypothesis is underlined in a paper by Alexander J. Probst et al.²², who first characterized the genus of *Forsterrea* as having a symbiotic lifestyle around nucleotide metabolism and Rubisco. Our findings suggest that the PRPP biosynthesis process is highly conserved in *Forsterrea*, indicating its crucial role in nucleotide metabolism. The conservation of nucleotide degradation genes in *Forsterrea* highlights its ability to break down nucleotides and recycle their components. We consider the possibility that *Forsterrea* depends on pyruvate oxidation to generate ATP²³ and provide metabolic intermediates to its host or other symbiotic partners.

The discovery of *Forsterrea's* metabolic capabilities using a metric to analyze large genomic datasets has revealed previously unknown information about the genus. The approach with identity scores used in this study proved to be effective and can be applied to any genomic dataset to infer information on the genus level. The process of data analysis can be simplified by condensing multiple unique genomes into genera, which allows for the inference of pathway conservancy and the discovery of novel microbial metabolic capabilities such as those found in *Forsterrea*.

Conclusion

Our metric has been shown to effectively assess the preservation of microbial metabolic pathways at the genus level among various bacterial and archaeal genera, as evidenced by our experimental trial. Focusing on genera proved a practical approach to studying microbial metabolic pathways. This approach made it easier to study the metabolic capacities of a group of genomes instead of analyzing each genome

individually. We gained a more comprehensive understanding of the metabolic pathways involved by examining a higher taxonomic level. Using identity scores instead of setting thresholds has proven to be a more effective way of representing pathway conservancy across microbial genera. This approach has been invaluable in showcasing not only the core pathways but also the secondary and accessory pathways of microorganisms. The use of identity scores considers the completeness of each genome and the quality of its pathways, thus providing a more nuanced understanding of pathway conservancy. Thresholds, on the other hand, tend to give the perception of non-conserved pathways, which could be attributed to low genome completeness. The archaeal genus *Forsterrea* is a perfect example of the potential benefits of using a non-threshold analytical approach. Only then could we discover the significance of its nucleotide metabolism and drive new insights about its potential symbiotic lifestyle. We hope that with our metric, we can support researchers in identifying variations in the metabolic capabilities of microbes that could impact microbial community dynamics and ecosystem functioning. It proved to be an efficient tool that can aid in better understanding the role of microbes in their ecosystem, thereby contributing to a more comprehensive and holistic view of their ecology.

I would like to express my gratitude to Prof. Dr. A. Murat Eren for providing us with the opportunity to gain a glimpse in his lab. I would also like to extend my thanks to Dr. Iva Veseli for her creative input and support throughout this project. . I am grateful to the Max Planck Institute for Marine Microbiology and Marmic coordination for making this lab rotation possible. Many thanks to my lab rotation partner, Brandon Marcus Hutt, whose creative inputs and knowledge of microbial metabolisms were invaluable during this project. . Finally, I want to express my gratitude to Max for his invaluable contributions to our algorithm. His insights will never cease to broaden our scientific horizon.

Conservancy of metabolic pathways across microbial genera

Figure 3 Conservancy of metabolic pathways of microbial genera with a threshold approach

The genomes belonged to five bacterial genera (CAIXRL01, Sporolactobacillus, Thermodesulfobacterium, Synechococcus, and PALSA) and five archaeal genera (JAJYZA01, Loki, Forterrea, Methanothermobacter, BMS3B). Some fundamental metabolic pathways, such as Glycolysis and pyrimidine ribonucleotide biosynthesis, remained relatively similar across all genera. The genera of Forterrea and JAJYZA01 appear to have lost all or a significant portion of their metabolic conservancy. Methanothermobacter and BMS3B share many similarities in their metabolic pathways, which overlap with their phylogenetic relationship. The same statement applies to the Synechococcus and PALSA genera.

Figure 5 Conservancy of metabolic pathways of microbial genera with the use of identity scores

The genomes belonged to five bacterial genera (CAIXRL01, Sporolactobacillus, Thermodesulfobacterium, Synechococcus, and PALSA) and five archaeal genera (JAJYZA01, Loki, Forterrea, Methanothermobacter, BMS3B). Using identity scores, we present a more detailed view of metabolic pathways, including core, secondary, and accessory pathways, found in the microbial genera. The PRPP pathway is the most conserved of all genera, followed closely by glycolysis and pyruvate oxidation. By analyzing the heatmap, we can see that in Forterrea, PRPP, pyruvate oxidation, and nucleotide degradation pathways are highly conserved, especially when we exclude data filtering. This highlights their potential importance in the metabolic repertoire of the genus

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Additional Material

Code (R version 4.3.0 (2023-04-21))

```

1. #EXPLORATORY PHASE -----
2.
3. #'GOAL:work with conserved subsets on full pathway level
4. #'
5. #'Start metric: genus level and conserved full glycolysis and photosynthesis pathway,
6. #'pathwise pathway analysis (looking at all branching options and taking one with most
7. #'completeness)
8. #'Genus of interest: Plochlorococcus clade
9. #'(not counting those from subclades like g__Prochlorococcus_A or g__Prochlorococcus_B)
10. #'Pseudomonas Clade (First 15 genomes)
11.
12.
13. #'Subgoal 1: Filter all datasets for glycolysis and photosynthesis pathway
14. #'Assign taxonomic identity
15. #'We have 28 genome matrix files
16. #'Taxonomic clarifications are in subset_metadata.txt
17. #'Test with GCA_002386445_1_modules
18.
19. setwd("")
20. install.packages("tidyverse")
21. library(tidyverse)
22. library(ggplot2)
23.
24. metadata <- read.table("subset_metadata.txt", header = TRUE, sep = "\t", fill = TRUE)
25. #Curate the metadata IDs
26. metadata$accession <- gsub("GB_", "", metadata$accession) # Remove "GB_"
27. metadata$accession <- gsub("RS_", "", metadata$accession)
28. metadata$accession <- gsub("\\.", "_", metadata$accession) #Change the dot to an underscore
29. #Read file with extracted genomes
30. first_data <- read.csv("First_Approximation.csv", header = TRUE)
31. first_data <- first_data[-c(55:87), ]
32. first_data$Taxonomia <- factor(first_data$Taxonomia)
33. first_data$Pathwaycode <- factor(first_data$Pathwaycode)
34. first_data$Pathway <- factor(first_data$Pathway)
35.
36. #-----
37.
38. #Merge First_Data and Metadata to extract the completeness score of the Genomes
39. merged_data <- merge(first_data, metadata, by.x = "GenomeID", by.y = "accession", all.x =
TRUE)
40. merged_data$Pathway <- factor(merged_data$Pathway)
41. merged_data$GenomeID <- factor(merged_data$GenomeID, levels = unique(merged_data$GenomeID))
42.
43.
44.
45. ggplot(merged_data, aes(x = checkm_completeness, y = Pathwise.score,)) +
46.   geom_point() + # Scatter plot
47.   scale_y_continuous(limits = c(0, 1), breaks = seq(0, 1, by = 0.1)) + # Y-axis limits and
breaks
48.   labs(x = "Completeness %", y = "Pathwise score", color = "Pathway") + # Axis and legend
labels
49.   theme_minimal()
50.
51.
52.
53.
54.
55.
56. # Add a line at the height of 0 (Null Hypothesis) in red
57. null_hypothesis_line <- geom_hline(yintercept = 0, color = "red")
58. merged_data$Diff <- merged_data$checkm_completeness - (merged_data$Pathwise.score * 100)
59. print(merged_data$Diff)
60.
61. # Create plot
62. ggplot(merged_data, aes(x = checkm_completeness, y = Diff)) +

```

```

63. geom_point() +
64. geom_hline(yintercept = 0, color = "red") +
65. theme_bw() +
66. labs(x = "Genome Completeness", y = "ð(Completeness-Pathwise Score)") +
67. ggtitle("Deviation from Expected Distribution")
68.
69.
70.
71. #Look at Glycolysis Data -----
72. glycolysis_data <- merged_data[merged_data$Pathway == "Glycolysis", ]
73.
74. # Plot the filtered data
75. ggplot(glycolysis_data, aes(x = GenomeID)) +
76.   geom_point(aes(y = checkm_completeness, color = "Completeness [%]"), alpha = 0.8) +
77.   geom_point(aes(y = Pathwise.score * 100, color = "Pathwise Score"), alpha = 0.8) +
78.   scale_y_continuous(sec.axis = sec_axis(~./100, name = "Pathwise Score"), limits = c(0,
100)) +
79.   labs(x = "GenomeID", y = "Completeness", title = "Glycolysis") +
80.   scale_color_manual(name = "Variable", values = c("Completeness [%]" = "magenta",
"Pathwise Score" = "darkblue")) +
81.   theme(axis.text.x = element_text(angle = 90, vjust = 0.5, hjust = 1))
82.
83. #overwrite unused column with Difference between both
84. names(glycolysis_data)[names(glycolysis_data) == "completeness"] <- "Diff"
85. glycolysis_data$Diff <- glycolysis_data$checkm_completeness -
(glycolysis_data$Pathwise.score * 100)
86.
87. ggplot(glycolysis_data, aes(x= checkm_completeness))+
88.   geom_point(aes(y= Diff))
89.
90.
91. #Look at Distribution of the Glyco Data
92.
93. # Add a line at the height of 0 (Null Hypothesis) in red
94. null_hypothesis_line <- geom_hline(yintercept = 0, color = "red")
95.
96. # Create plot
97. ggplot(glycolysis_data, aes(x = checkm_completeness, y = Diff)) +
98.   geom_point() +
99.   geom_hline(yintercept = 0, color = "red") +
100.  theme_bw() +
101.  labs(x = "Genome Completeness", y = "ð(Pathwise Score-Completeness)") +
102.  ggtitle("Deviation from Expected Distribution Glycolysis")
103.
104.
105.
106.
107. #Look at Photosynthesis Data -----
108. #Photosystems I
109.
110. photosystem_data <- merged_data[merged_data$Pathway == "Photosystem" & merged_data$Specific
== "I", ]
111.
112. # Plot the filtered data
113. ggplot(photosystem_data, aes(x = GenomeID)) +
114.   geom_point(aes(y = checkm_completeness, color = "Completeness [%]")) +
115.   geom_point(aes(y = Pathwise.score * 100, color = "Pathwise Score")) +
116.   scale_y_continuous(sec.axis = sec_axis(~./100, name = "Pathwise Score"), limits = c(0,
100)) +
117.   labs(x = "GenomeID", y = "Completeness", title = "Photosystem I") +
118.   scale_color_manual(name = "Variable", values = c("Completeness [%]" = "darkgreen",
"Pathwise Score" = "lightgreen")) +
119.   theme(axis.text.x = element_text(angle = 90, vjust = 0.5, hjust = 1))
120.
121. #Photosystem II
122. photosystem_data <- merged_data[merged_data$Pathway == "Photosystem" & merged_data$Specific
== "II", ]
123.
124. # Plot the filtered data
125. ggplot(photosystem_data, aes(x = GenomeID)) +

```

```

126. geom_point(aes(y = checkm_completeness, color = "Completeness [%]")) +
127. geom_point(aes(y = Pathwise.score * 100, color = "Pathwise Score")) +
128. scale_y_continuous(sec.axis = sec_axis(~./100, name = "Pathwise Score"), limits = c(0,
100)) +
129. labs(x = "GenomeID", y = "Completeness", title = "Photosystem II") +
130. scale_color_manual(name = "Variable", values = c("Completeness [%]" = "darkgreen",
"Pathwise Score" = "lightgreen")) +
131. theme(axis.text.x = element_text(angle = 90, vjust = 0.5, hjust = 1))
132.
133.
134. #-----
135. #Playing with PCA and Data inspection
136. library(vegan)
137. library(corrgram)
138. summary(merged_data)
139.
140. #I want to perform a PCA with checkm_contamination, checkm_completeness and
141. #contig_count and with Pathwise.score
142. library(dplyr)
143.
144. PCA_contamination <- subset(merged_data, select = c("Pathwise.score",
145.                                                    "checkm_completeness",
146.                                                    "checkm_contamination",
147.                                                    "contig_count"))
148. merged_PCA <- rda(
149.   PCA_contamination,
150.   scale = TRUE
151. )
152. biplot(merged_PCA, choices = c(1,2,3,4), scaling=-1)
153.
154.
155. #'Now Im going to try and look at everything, maybe its messy maybe it isn't
156. #Taking everything which is numeric into consideration
157. numeric_merged_data <- select_if(merged_data, is.numeric)
158. numeric_merged_data <- na.omit(numeric_merged_data)
159.
160. merged_numeric_PCA <- rda(
161.   numeric_merged_data,
162.   scale = TRUE,
163.   na.rm = TRUE
164. )
165.
166. biplot(merged_numeric_PCA, choices = c(1,2,3,4), scaling=-1)
167.
168.
169. library(scatterplot3d)
170. # Exclude the "Diff" column from the numeric dataset
171. numeric_merged_data <- numeric_merged_data[, !colnames(numeric_merged_data) %in% "Diff"]
172.
173. # Now, you can perform NMDS analysis on the updated dataset
174. myNmDS <- metaMDS(comm = numeric_merged_data, distance = "bray", k = 2, trymax = 20, trace
= FALSE)
175. plot(myNmDS, type="t")
176. plot(myNmDS, type = "t", xlim = c(-0, 0.1), ylim = c(0, 0.2))
177.
178.
179. #-----
180. #Looking at the Capser Package and what it can do
181.
182.
183. install.packages("caper")
184. install.packages("ape")
185. install.packages("mvtnorm")
186. install.packages("MASS")
187.
188. library("caper")
189. library("ape")
190. library("mvtnorm")
191. library("MASS")
192.

```

```

193.
194.
195.
196. #-----
197. #Playing with PCA and Data inspection
198. library(vegan)
199. library(corrgram)
200. summary(merged_data)
201.
202. #I want to perform a PCA with checkm_contamination, checkm_completeness and
203. #contig_count and with Pathwise.score
204. library(dplyr)
205.
206. PCA_contamination <- subset(merged_data, select = c("Pathwise.score",
207.                                                    "checkm_completeness",
208.                                                    "checkm_contamination",
209.                                                    "contig_count"))
210. merged_PCA <- rda(
211.   PCA_contamination,
212.   scale = TRUE
213. )
214. biplot(merged_PCA, choices = c(1,2,3,4), scaling=-1)
215.
216.
217. #Now Im going to try and look at everything, maybe its messy maybe it isn't
218. #Taking everything which is numeric into consideration
219. numeric_merged_data <- select_if(merged_data, is.numeric)
220. numeric_merged_data <- na.omit(numeric_merged_data)
221.
222. merged_numeric_PCA <- rda(
223.   numeric_merged_data,
224.   scale = TRUE,
225.   na.rm = TRUE
226. )
227.
228. biplot(merged_numeric_PCA, choices = c(1,2,3,4), scaling=-1)
229.
230.
231. library(scatterplot3d)
232. # Exclude the "Diff" column from the numeric dataset
233. numeric_merged_data <- numeric_merged_data[, !colnames(numeric_merged_data) %in% "Diff"]
234.
235. # Now, you can perform NMDS analysis on the updated dataset
236. myNmDS <- metaMDS(comm = numeric_merged_data, distance = "bray", k = 2, trymax = 20, trace
= FALSE)
237. plot(myNmDS,type="t")
238. plot(myNmDS, type = "t", xlim = c(-0, 0.1), ylim = c(0, 0.2))
239.
240.
241.
242.
243.
244.
245.
246. #-----
247. #' First possibility to summarize our data without
248. #' deciding on thresholds involving probability calculation
249. #'
250. #' Case 1: High completeness score C and high pathwise score P
251. #' high probability I that this will be TRUE
252. #'
253. #' Case 2: High C, low P
254. #' high probability I that this will be FALSE
255. #'
256. #' Case 3: Low C, High P
257. #' high I that this will be TRUE
258. #'
259. #' Case 4: Low C, low P
260. #' low I, since it could be TRUE or FALSE, as we don't have enough C to know
261. #'

```

```

262. #' We will affect number 4 by giving it far less power in the end calculation
263.
264.
265.
266. #-----
267.
268. # Function to calculate species means for a given pathway
269. calculate_species_means <- function(data, pathway) {
270.   # Subset data for the given pathway
271.   pathway_data <- data[data$Pathway == pathway, ]
272.
273.   # Identify unique GenomeIDs
274.   unique_genome_ids <- unique(pathway_data$GenomeID)
275.
276.   # Initialize a list to store species means
277.   species_means <- list()
278.
279.   # Iterate through each unique GenomeID
280.   for (gid in unique_genome_ids) {
281.     # Subset data for the current GenomeID
282.     subset_data <- pathway_data[pathway_data$GenomeID == gid, ]
283.
284.     # Extract the genus from the taxonomy information
285.     genus <- gsub("^.*g__(\\w+).*", "\\1", subset_data$gtdb_taxonomy[1])
286.
287.     # Calculate identity score (Ii) for each genome
288.     identity_scores <- apply(subset_data[, c("Pathwise.score", "checkm_completeness")], 1,
289.                               max)
290.
291.     # Calculate the sum of squared identity scores
292.     sum_squared_identity <- sum(identity_scores^2)
293.
294.     # Calculate the weighted mean ( $\mu_{sp.i}$ ) for the species
295.     species_mean <- sum((identity_scores^2 / sum_squared_identity) *
296.                         subset_data$Pathwise.score)
297.
298.     # Store the species mean under the respective genus
299.     if (is.null(species_means[[genus]])) {
300.       species_means[[genus]] <- list()
301.     }
302.     species_means[[genus]][[paste("Species", length(species_means[[genus]]) + 1)]] <-
303.       species_mean
304.   }
305.   return(species_means)
306. }
307.
308. # Function to calculate genus means for all pathways and store in a matrix
309. calculate_genus_means_matrix_all_pathways <- function(data) {
310.   # Identify unique pathways
311.   unique_pathways <- unique(data$Pathway)
312.
313.   # Identify unique genera
314.   unique_genera <- unique(gsub("^.*g__(\\w+).*", "\\1", data$gtdb_taxonomy))
315.
316.   # Initialize a matrix to store genus means for all pathways
317.   genus_means_matrix <- matrix(0, nrow = length(unique_genera), ncol =
318.     length(unique_pathways),
319.     dimnames = list(unique_genera, unique_pathways))
320.
321.   # Iterate through each unique pathway
322.   for (pathway in unique_pathways) {
323.     # Calculate species means for the current pathway
324.     species_means <- calculate_species_means(data, pathway)
325.
326.     # Iterate through each unique genus
327.     for (genus in unique_genera) {
328.       # Check if the genus has species means calculated
329.       if (!is.null(species_means[[genus]])) {
330.         # Calculate the mean of species means for the genus

```

```

328.     genus_mean <- mean(unlist(species_means[[genus]]))
329.     # Store the genus mean in the matrix
330.     genus_means_matrix[genus, pathway] <- genus_mean
331.   }
332. }
333. }
334.
335. return(genus_means_matrix)
336. }
337.
338. # Calculate genus means matrix for all pathways
339. genus_means_matrix_all_pathways <- calculate_genus_means_matrix_all_pathways(merged_data)
340.
341. # Print genus means matrix for all pathways
342. print(genus_means_matrix_all_pathways)
343.
344.
345. #-----
346. #' Possibility 2, from the analysis, we define treshholds
347. #' >80% genome completeness as Threshold for our data and 75% pathwise score
348. #' identifid through graphical analysis and deviation from expected distribution
349.
350. path_75_80_completeness <- merged_data[merged_data$checkm_completeness >= 80,
351.                                         merged_data$Pathwise.score >= 0.75,]
352. head(path_75_80_completeness)
353. summary(path_75_80_completeness)
354.
355. #'Goal: we want to find a metric describing Pathwise score as a variable dependant
356. #'of the genome completeness (TRUE or FALSE boolean)
357. #'if the completeness isn't 100% we want to decrease the pathwise score a bit aswell
358. #'
359. #'
360. #'C as the genome completeness (in percentage)
361. #'P as the Pathwise score
362. #'Tc as the completeness threshold (e.g., 80%)
363. #'Tp as the Pathwise score threshold (e.g., 0.75)
364. #'TRUE = 1
365. #'FALSE = 0
366.
367. conservancy_function <- function(C, P, Tc = 80, Tp = 0.75) {
368.   print(paste("Completeness:", C)) # Print completeness value
369.   print(paste("Pathwise score:", P)) # Print Pathwise score value
370.   if (C < Tc) { #if our completeness is lower than our threshold, then
371.     print("Completeness below threshold")
372.     return(0)
373.   } else { #if completeness is higher or equal to 80% THEN
374.     adjust_pathwise_score <- Tp * (C / 100) #completeness * our threshold (0.75)
375.     print(paste("Adjusted Pathwise score threshold:", adjust_pathwise_score)) # Print
adjusted Pathwise score threshold
376.     if (P >= adjust_pathwise_score) {
377.       print("Pathwise score meets threshold")
378.       return(1)
379.     } else {
380.       print("Pathwise score does not meet threshold")
381.       return(0)
382.     }
383.   }
384. }
385.
386.
387.
388. # Create a new column "true_conservancy" in merged_data
389. merged_data$true_conservancy <- apply(merged_data, 1, function(row) {
390.   C <- as.numeric(row["checkm_completeness"]) # Convert completeness to numeric
391.   P <- as.numeric(row["Pathwise.score"])      # Convert Pathwise score to numeric
392.   result <- conservancy_function(C, P) # Call the function with correct parameters
393.   return(result)
394. })
395.
396. head(merged_data)

```

```

397. print(merged_data$true_conservancy)
398.
399.
400.
401. # Function to calculate species means for a given pathway based on true_conservancy
402. calculate_species_means_true_conservancy <- function(data, pathway) {
403.   # Subset data for the given pathway
404.   pathway_data <- data[data$Pathway == pathway, ]
405.
406.   # Identify unique GenomeIDs
407.   unique_genome_ids <- unique(pathway_data$GenomeID)
408.
409.   # Initialize a list to store species means
410.   species_means <- list()
411.
412.   # Iterate through each unique GenomeID
413.   for (gid in unique_genome_ids) {
414.     # Subset data for the current GenomeID
415.     subset_data <- pathway_data[pathway_data$GenomeID == gid, ]
416.
417.     # Extract the genus from the taxonomy information
418.     genus <- gsub("^.*g_(\\w+).*", "\\1", subset_data$gtdb_taxonomy[1])
419.
420.     # Calculate species mean based on true_conservancy
421.     species_mean <- sum(subset_data$true_conservancy) /
length(unique(subset_data$GenomeID))
422.
423.     # Store the species mean under the respective genus
424.     if (is.null(species_means[[genus]])) {
425.       species_means[[genus]] <- list()
426.     }
427.     species_means[[genus]][[paste("Species", length(species_means[[genus]]) + 1)]] <-
species_mean
428.   }
429.
430.   return(species_means)
431. }
432.
433. # Function to calculate genus means for all pathways and store in a matrix (using the new
method)
434. calculate_genus_means_matrix_all_pathways_true_conservancy <- function(data) {
435.   # Identify unique pathways
436.   unique_pathways <- unique(data$Pathway)
437.
438.   # Identify unique genera
439.   unique_genera <- unique(gsub("^.*g_(\\w+).*", "\\1", data$gtdb_taxonomy))
440.
441.   # Initialize a matrix to store genus means for all pathways
442.   genus_means_matrix <- matrix(0, nrow = length(unique_genera), ncol =
length(unique_pathways),
443.                                dimnames = list(unique_genera, unique_pathways))
444.
445.   # Iterate through each unique pathway
446.   for (pathway in unique_pathways) {
447.     # Calculate species means for the current pathway using the new method
448.     species_means <- calculate_species_means_true_conservancy(data, pathway)
449.
450.     # Iterate through each unique genus
451.     for (genus in unique_genera) {
452.       # Check if the genus has species means calculated
453.       if (!is.null(species_means[[genus]])) {
454.         # Calculate the mean of species means for the genus
455.         genus_mean <- mean(unlist(species_means[[genus]]))
456.         # Store the genus mean in the matrix
457.         genus_means_matrix[genus, pathway] <- genus_mean
458.       }
459.     }
460.   }
461.
462.   return(genus_means_matrix)

```

```

463. }
464.
465. # Calculate genus means matrix for all pathways using the new method
466. genus_means_matrix_all_pathways_true_conservancy <-
calculate_genus_means_matrix_all_pathways_true_conservancy(merged_data)
467.
468. # Print genus means matrix for all pathways
469. print(genus_means_matrix_all_pathways_true_conservancy)
470.
471. #-----
472.
473. #WORKING WITH LARGER DATASETS
474.
475. #-----
476.
477. setwd("")
478.
479. library(dplyr)
480. library(stringr)
481.
482.
483. #Read in metadata file and adapt genome IDs to match dataset
484. #metadata <- read.table("subset_metadata.txt", header = TRUE, sep = "\t", fill = TRUE)
485. #metadata$accession <- gsub("GB_", "", metadata$accession) # Remove "GB_"
486. #metadata$accession <- gsub("RS_", "", metadata$accession)
487. #metadata$accession <- gsub("\\.", "_", metadata$accession) #Change the dot to an
underscore
488.
489.
490.
491. #Read genome containing file
492. first_data <- read.table("all_modules_metadata_with_headers.txt", sep = "\t", fill = TRUE,
header = TRUE)
493. #first_data <- first_data[, -3]
494.
495.
496. # Vector of new column names to match code
497. new_names <- c("GenomeID", "checkm_completeness", "gtdb_taxonomy", "Pathwaycode",
"Pathway", "Pathwise.score") # Replace 'New_Column1', 'New_Column2', etc. with your new column
names
498. colnames(first_data) <- new_names
499.
500.
501.
502. # Change genus names to GTDB databank names
503. mappings <- c(
504.   "g_WH-5701" = "g_Synechococcus",
505.   "g_Vulcanococcus" = "g_Synechococcus",
506.   "g_QBMD01" = "g_Synechococcus",
507.   "g_Cyanobium_A" = "g_Synechococcus",
508.   "g_MW101C3" = "g_Synechococcus",
509.   "g_Cyanobium" = "g_Synechococcus",
510.   "g_NIES-981" = "g_Synechococcus",
511.   "g_CBW1002" = "g_Synechococcus",
512.   "g_RSCCF101" = "g_Synechococcus",
513.   "g_Synechococcus_C" = "g_Synechococcus",
514.   "g_Parasynechococcus" = "g_Synechococcus",
515.   "g_RCC307" = "g_Synechococcus",
516.   "g_Synechococcus_D" = "g_Synechococcus",
517.   "g_Synechococcus_B" = "g_Synechococcus",
518.   "g_Synechococcus_A" = "g_Synechococcus",
519.   "g_BAIKAL-G1" = "g_Synechococcus",
520.   "g_PCC-6312" = "g_Synechococcus",
521.   "g_Thermostichus" = "g_Synechococcus",
522.   "g_Phormidesmis" = "g_Synechococcus",
523.   "g_Limnothrix" = "g_Synechococcus",
524.   "g_BMS3Bbin07" = "g_Thermodesulfobacterium",
525.   "g_BMS3Bbin08" = "g_Thermodesulfobacterium",
526.   "g_BMS3Bbin05" = "g_Thermodesulfobacterium",
527.   "g_BMS3Bbin11" = "g_Thermodesulfobacterium",

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528. "g_BMS3Bbin01" = "g_PALSA-1178",
529. "g_BMS3BBIN02" = "g_PALSA-1178",
530. "g_BMS3BBIN04" = "g_Sporolactobacillus",
531. "g_Methanothermobacter_A" = "g_Methanothermobacter",
532. "g_CAIQIA01" = "g_Synechococcus",
533. "g_PCC-7502" = "g_Synechococcus",
534. "g_PCC-7336" = "g_Synechococcus",
535. "g_PCC" = "g_Synechococcus"
536. )
537.
538. # Loop through the mappings and replace each pattern in the "gtdb_taxonomy" column
539. for (pattern in names(mappings)) {
540.   first_data$gtdb_taxonomy <- str_replace_all(first_data$gtdb_taxonomy, paste0("(?<=;)",
541.   pattern, "(?=<|$)"), mappings[pattern])
542. }
543.
544. #Cleaning dataset
545.
546. # Remove entries where gtdb_taxonomy contains "g_Gloeomargarita"
547. first_data <- first_data %>%
548.   filter(!grepl("g_Gloeomargarita", gtdb_taxonomy))
549.
550. # Remove entries where GenomeID contains "GCF_000332275_1"
551. first_data <- first_data %>%
552.   filter(!grepl("GCF_000332275_1", GenomeID))
553.
554. # View the updated dataframe
555. View(first_data)
556.
557.
558.
559. first_data$Taxonomia <- factor(first_data$Taxonomia)
560. first_data$Pathwaycode <- factor(first_data$Pathwaycode)
561. first_data$Pathway <- factor(first_data$Pathway)
562. first_data <- na.omit(first_data)
563. #-----
564.
565. #Merge First_Data and Metadata to extract the completeness score of the Genomes
566.
567. #merged_data <- merge(first_data, metadata, by.x = "GenomeID", by.y = "accession", all.x =
568. TRUE)
569. #Assuming your dataset is named "your_data"
570. #first_data <- na.omit(first_data)
571.
572.
573. #-----
574. #' First possibility to summarize our data without
575. #' deciding on thresholds involving probability calculation
576. #'
577. #' Case 1: High completeness score C and high pathwise score P
578. #' high probability I that this will be TRUE
579. #'
580. #' Case 2: High C, low P
581. #' high probability I that this will be FALSE
582. #'
583. #' Case 3: Low C, High P
584. #' high I that this will be TRUE
585. #'
586. #' Case 4: Low C, low P
587. #' low I, since it could be TRUE or FALSE, as we don't have enough C to know
588. #'
589. #' We will affect number 4 by giving it far less power in the end calculation
590.
591.
592.
593. #-----
594. # Function to calculate species means for a given pathway
595. calculate_species_means <- function(data, pathway) {

```

```

596. # Subset data for the given pathway
597. pathway_data <- data[data$Pathway == pathway, ]
598.
599. # Identify unique GenomeIDs
600. unique_genome_ids <- unique(pathway_data$GenomeID)
601.
602. # Initialize a list to store species means
603. species_means <- list()
604.
605. # Iterate through each unique GenomeID
606. for (gid in unique_genome_ids) {
607.   # Subset data for the current GenomeID
608.   subset_data <- pathway_data[pathway_data$GenomeID == gid, ]
609.
610.   # Extract the genus from the taxonomy information
611.   genus <- gsub("^.*g_(\\w+).*", "\\1", subset_data$gtdb_taxonomy[1])
612.
613.   # Calculate identity score (Ii) for each genome
614.   identity_scores <- apply(subset_data[, c("Pathwise.score", "checkm_completeness")], 1,
615. max)
616.
617.   # Calculate the sum of squared identity scores
618.   sum_squared_identity <- sum(identity_scores^2)
619.
620.   # Calculate the weighted mean ( $\mu_{sp.i}$ ) for the species
621.   species_mean <- sum((identity_scores^2 / sum_squared_identity) *
622. subset_data$Pathwise.score)
623.
624.   # Store the species mean under the respective genus
625.   if (is.null(species_means[[genus]])) {
626.     species_means[[genus]] <- list()
627.   }
628.   species_means[[genus]][[paste("Species", length(species_means[[genus]]) + 1)]] <-
629. species_mean
630. }
631.
632. # Function to calculate genus means for all pathways and store in a matrix
633. calculate_genus_means_matrix_all_pathways <- function(data) {
634.   # Identify unique pathways
635.   unique_pathways <- unique(data$Pathway)
636.
637.   # Identify unique genera
638.   unique_genera <- unique(gsub("^.*g_(\\w+).*", "\\1", data$gtdb_taxonomy))
639.
640.   # Initialize a matrix to store genus means for all pathways
641.   genus_means_matrix <- matrix(0, nrow = length(unique_genera), ncol =
642. length(unique_pathways),
643.                               dimnames = list(unique_genera, unique_pathways))
644.
645.   # Iterate through each unique pathway
646.   for (pathway in unique_pathways) {
647.     # Calculate species means for the current pathway
648.     species_means <- calculate_species_means(data, pathway)
649.
650.     # Iterate through each unique genus
651.     for (genus in unique_genera) {
652.       # Check if the genus has species means calculated
653.       if (!is.null(species_means[[genus]])) {
654.         # Calculate the mean of species means for the genus
655.         genus_mean <- mean(unlist(species_means[[genus]]))
656.         # Store the genus mean in the matrix
657.         genus_means_matrix[genus, pathway] <- genus_mean
658.       }
659.     }
660.   }
661.   return(genus_means_matrix)

```

```

662. }
663.
664. # Calculate genus means matrix for all pathways
665. genus_means_matrix_all_pathways <- calculate_genus_means_matrix_all_pathways(first_data)
666.
667. # Print genus means matrix for all pathways
668. print(genus_means_matrix_all_pathways)
669.
670.
671. #Save it in variable without_treshholds for clarity
672. without_treshholds <- genus_means_matrix_all_pathways
673.
674.
675.
676. #-----
677. #' Possibility 2, from the analysis, we define treshholds
678. #' >80% genome completeness as Threshold for our data and 75% pathwise score
679. #' identifid through graphical analysis and deviation from expected distribution
680.
681. path_75_80_completeness <- first_data[first_data$checkm_completeness >= 80 &
682.                                     first_data$Pathwise.score >= 0.75, ]
683.
684. head(path_75_80_completeness)
685. summary(path_75_80_completeness)
686.
687. #'Goal: we want to find a metric describing Pathwise score as a variable dependant
688. #'of the genome completeness (TRUE or FALSE boolean)
689. #'if the completeness isn't 100% we want to decrease the pathwise score a bit aswell
690. #'
691. #'
692. #'C as the genome completeness (in percentage)
693. #'P as the Pathwise score
694. #'Tc as the completeness threshold (e.g., 80%)
695. #'Tp as the Pathwise score threshold (e.g., 0.75)
696. #'TRUE = 1
697. #'FALSE = 0
698.
699. conservancy_function <- function(C, P, Tc = 80, Tp = 0.75) {
700.   print(paste("Completeness:", C)) # Print completeness value
701.   print(paste("Pathwise score:", P)) # Print Pathwise score value
702.   if (C < Tc) { #if our completeness is lower than our threshold, then
703.     print("Completeness below threshold")
704.     return(0)
705.   } else { #if completeness is higher or equal to 80% THEN
706.     adjust_pathwise_score <- Tp * (C / 100) #completeness * our threshold (0.75)
707.     print(paste("Adjusted Pathwise score threshold:", adjust_pathwise_score)) # Print
adjusted Pathwise score threshold
708.     if (P >= adjust_pathwise_score) {
709.       print("Pathwise score meets threshold")
710.       return(1)
711.     } else {
712.       print("Pathwise score does not meet threshold")
713.       return(0)
714.     }
715.   }
716. }
717.
718.
719.
720. # Create a new column "true_conservancy" in merged_data
721. first_data$true_conservancy <- apply(first_data, 1, function(row) {
722.   C <- as.numeric(row["checkm_completeness"]) # Convert completeness to numeric
723.   P <- as.numeric(row["Pathwise.score"]) # Convert Pathwise score to numeric
724.   result <- conservancy_function(C, P) # Call the function with correct parameters
725.   return(result)
726. })
727.
728. head(first_data)
729. print(first_data$true_conservancy)
730.

```

```

731.
732.
733. # Function to calculate species means for a given pathway based on true_conservancy
734. calculate_species_means_true_conservancy <- function(data, pathway) {
735. # Subset data for the given pathway
736. pathway_data <- data[data$Pathway == pathway, ]
737.
738. # Identify unique GenomeIDs
739. unique_genome_ids <- unique(pathway_data$GenomeID)
740.
741. # Initialize a list to store species means
742. species_means <- list()
743.
744. # Iterate through each unique GenomeID
745. for (gid in unique_genome_ids) {
746. # Subset data for the current GenomeID
747. subset_data <- pathway_data[pathway_data$GenomeID == gid, ]
748.
749. # Extract the genus from the taxonomy information
750. genus <- gsub("^.*g__(\\w+).*", "\\1", subset_data$gtdb_taxonomy[1])
751.
752. # Calculate species mean based on true_conservancy
753. species_mean <- sum(subset_data$true_conservancy) /
length(unique(subset_data$GenomeID))
754.
755. # Store the species mean under the respective genus
756. if (is.null(species_means[[genus]])) {
757. species_means[[genus]] <- list()
758. }
759. species_means[[genus]][[paste("Species", length(species_means[[genus]]) + 1)]] <-
species_mean
760. }
761.
762. return(species_means)
763. }
764.
765. # Function to calculate genus means for all pathways and store in a matrix (using the new
method)
766. calculate_genus_means_matrix_all_pathways_true_conservancy <- function(data) {
767. # Identify unique pathways
768. unique_pathways <- unique(data$Pathway)
769.
770. # Identify unique genera
771. unique_genera <- unique(gsub("^.*g__(\\w+).*", "\\1", data$gtdb_taxonomy))
772.
773. # Initialize a matrix to store genus means for all pathways
774. genus_means_matrix <- matrix(0, nrow = length(unique_genera), ncol =
length(unique_pathways),
775.                               dimnames = list(unique_genera, unique_pathways))
776.
777. # Iterate through each unique pathway
778. for (pathway in unique_pathways) {
779. # Calculate species means for the current pathway using the new method
780. species_means <- calculate_species_means_true_conservancy(data, pathway)
781.
782. # Iterate through each unique genus
783. for (genus in unique_genera) {
784. # Check if the genus has species means calculated
785. if (!is.null(species_means[[genus]])) {
786. # Calculate the mean of species means for the genus
787. genus_mean <- mean(unlist(species_means[[genus]]))
788. # Store the genus mean in the matrix
789. genus_means_matrix[genus, pathway] <- genus_mean
790. }
791. }
792. }
793.
794. return(genus_means_matrix)
795. }
796.

```

```

797. # Calculate genus means matrix for all pathways using the new method
798. genus_means_matrix_all_pathways_true_conservancy_threshold <-
calculate_genus_means_matrix_all_pathways_true_conservancy(first_data)
799.
800. # Print genus means matrix for all pathways
801. print(genus_means_matrix_all_pathways_true_conservancy)
802.
803.
804. #save it in variable with_thresholds for clarity
805. with_treshholds <- genus_means_matrix_all_pathways_true_conservancy_threshold
806.
807.
808. #Export Matrix to a CSV-----
809.
810. write.csv(with_treshholds, file = "with_thresholds.csv")
811. write.csv(without_treshholds, file = "without_thresholds.csv")
812.
813.
814. #visualizing data as a heat map-----
815. install.packages("gplots") # Install gplots package for heatmap functionality
816. library(gplots)
817. install.packages("viridis")
818. library(viridis)
819. install.packages("ape")
820. library(ape)
821. library(dendextend)
822.
823. #Use both Methods and get heatmap data
824. # Load necessary packages if not already loaded
825. if (!requireNamespace("gplots", quietly = TRUE)) {
826.   install.packages("gplots")
827. }
828. library(gplots)
829.
830. #Max code
831. #Use both Methods and get heatmap data
832. heat_data_list <- list(with = with_treshholds_sorted,without = without_treshholds_sorted)
833. for (name_heat_data in names(heat_data_list)) {
834.   heat_data <- heat_data_list[[name_heat_data]]
835.   print(dim(heat_data))
836.
837.   ## Get column names of the heat_data
838.   #col_names <- colnames(heat_data)
839.
840.   # Define a function to extract substring before the first comma
841.   shorten_label <- function(label) {
842.     # Find the position of the first comma
843.     comma_pos <- regexpr(",", label)
844.
845.     # Extract substring before the first comma
846.     if (comma_pos != -1) {
847.       label <- substr(label, 1, comma_pos - 1)
848.     }
849.
850.     return(label)
851.   }
852.
853.   #shorten_label <- function(label){
854.     # # Find the position of the first comma
855.     # comma_pos <- regexpr(",", label)
856.     # # Extract substring before the first comma
857.     # if (comma_pos != -1) {
858.     #   print("ok")
859.     #   short_label <- substr(label, 1, comma_pos - 1)
860.     #   print("ok")
861.     #   short_label <- mapply(short_label,label,0,comma_pos,mod_label)
862.     #   print("ok")
863.     #   short_label_list <- append(label_list, short_label)
864.     #   print("ok")
865.     #   label <- short_label

```

```

866. # }
867. # return(label)
868. #}
869. #
870. #mod_label <- function(short_label,label,c,comma_pos){
871. # print(short_label)
872. # if (!short_label %in% short_label_list){
873. #   return(short_label)
874. # }else if(comma_pos + c > nchar(label)){
875. #   short_label <- paste(label, "I", sep="")
876. #   c <- c + 1
877. #   short_label <- mapply(short_label,label,c,comma_pos,mod_label)
878. # }else{
879. #   after_comma <- substr(label, comma_pos - 1 + c, comma_pos + c)
880. #   short_label <- paste(label, after_comma, sep="")
881. #   c <- c + 1
882. #   short_label <- mapply(short_label,label,c,comma_pos,mod_label)
883. # }
884. #}
885.
886. # Sort Columns
887. sorted_heat_data <- heat_data[order(rownames(heat_data)) ,order(colnames(heat_data))]
888.
889. #read phylogenetic tree as reference map
890. phylo_tree <- read.tree("phylogenomic-tree_edited.txt")
891. phylo_tree$edge.length <- NULL
892.
893. # Get row labels from heatmap data
894. row_labels <- rownames(sorted_heat_data)
895.
896. # Reorder row labels based on the order of tips in the phylogenetic tree
897. row_labels <- row_labels[match(phylo_tree$tip.label, row_labels)]
898.
899. ## Reorder rows of heatmap data
900. #sorted_heat_data <- sorted_heat_data[match(row_labels, rownames(sorted_heat_data)), ]
901.
902. # Define the order of genera on the y-axis
903. genus_order <- c("PALSA", "Synechococcus", "Thermodesulfobacterium", "BMS3B",
904. "Methanothermobacter", "Forterre", "Loki", "JAJYZA01", "Sporolactobacillus", "CAIXRL01")
905.
906. # Reorder rows based on the defined order of genera
907. sorted_heat_data <- sorted_heat_data[match(genus_order, rownames(heat_data)), ]
908.
909. # Create distance matrix
910. dist_matrix <- dist(sorted_heat_data)
911.
912. # Create dendrogram for rows with row names from sorted_heat_data
913. row_dend <- as.dendrogram(hclust(dist_matrix, method = "complete"), labels =
914. labels(phylo_tree)[row_order])
915.
916. # Apply the function to each column name
917. # Get column names of the heat_data
918. col_names <- colnames(sorted_heat_data)
919.
920. #short_label_list <- list()
921. shortened_pathways <- sapply(col_names, shorten_label)
922.
923. ## Set row names for the dendrogram
924. #rownames(row_dend) <- row_labels
925.
926. ## Create dendrogram for rows
927. #row_dend <- sorted_heat_data %>%
928. # dist() %>%
929. # hclust() %>%
930. # as.dendrogram() %>%
931. # set("branches_lwd", 1)
932.
933. print(rownames(sorted_heat_data))
934. print("Dend")
935. print(phylo_tree$tip.label)

```

Conservancy of metabolic pathways across microbial genera

```
934. print("---")
935. print(row_labels)
936. print("---")
937. print(labels(row_dend))
938. print("----")
939.
940. ## Map row labels to corresponding branches in dendrogram
941. #mapped_row_labels <- match(rownames(row_dend), row_labels)
942.
943. # Plot the heatmap
944. title = paste("conservancy of methabolic pathways of microbial genera (",name_heat_data,"
threshold)",sep = '')
945. heatmap.2(as.matrix(sorted_heat_data),
946.           col = viridis(n = 256),      # Use defined color palette with 256 colors
947.           dendrogram = "none",        # Show only row dendrogram 'row'
948.           Rowv = FALSE,               # Row dendrogram
949.
950.
951.
```